

Analyzing multiple response data through a signal-detection framework

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Abstract

Multiple response formats are well suited for assessing the construct of cue recognition, the discrimination between information that is relevant or irrelevant to a decision. One useful approach to analyzing cue recognition data is through a signal-detection measurement model. This paper investigates the ideal number of candidates and cues required to achieve reasonable measurements.

Analyzing multiple response data through a signal-detection framework

As contemporary exams modernize, test design evolves. Typically, this results in the inclusion of a wider range of item types, and there are various motives for doing so. One reason is that the advancement of technology allows psychologists and psychometricians to develop item types that increase test fidelity (Parshall, Harmes, Davey, & Pashley, 2010). In the medical field, for example, practical exams include fully digitized and interactive manikins, which record data and feedback digitally (Rosen, McBride, & Drake, 2009). The increase in overlap between assessment and application strengthens the test's ecological validity. Thus, technology not only allows for richer data collection, but also promotes test fidelity.

Another important reason to include new item types in test design is to better assess underlying constructs for which the test is intended to measure. Again, the contributions of technology allow for this. Some higher level cognitive constructs are not best suited for paper and pencil multiple choice questions and instead are better measured through interactive items. Although technology enhanced items might have a fidelity and assessment advantage over tradition items, psychologists and psychometricians must carefully investigate the complexities of new items.

Some of these complexities include usability issues, differential item functioning, and scoring issues. Usability issues are brought about when, paradoxically, the technology used to enhance items prevents items from measuring the intended construct: The introduced technology is too complex for the testing population. Researchers investigate this complexity through usability studies by administering technology enhanced items to a small sample of the testing population. Critically, the collected feedback allows researchers to refine the item structure so examinees can intuitively use and navigate through the item features.

Closely related to usability complications is the potential to introduce artifacts that give rise to differential item functioning. Specifically, the technology used to enhance items might be more prevalent in some groups than others and thus disadvantage the group of examinees who are not familiar with the

technology. A group of students who were trained with interactive manikins might perform better than those trained without simply because of their prior exposure and familiarity with the assessment technology. To prevent these issues, researchers conduct moderate scale pilot studies with purposeful sampling, sampling from groups likely to differ as a function of the introduced technology.

Lastly, when introducing technology enhanced items, test developers must consider viable scoring methods, especially if the intended goal of the item type is to better measure an underlying construct. Under these situations, it is reasonable to assume that conventional scoring models might not suffice. Therefore, the prudent test developer must consider alternative scoring methods. The current paper focuses on this topic—the viability of an alternative scoring model for a technology enhanced multiple response item type.

Multiple response item types

Figure 1 displays several item types across a range of constraints. Of conventional item types, a two-alternative forced-choice item is one of the most constrained item types. A true-false item is the most widely used two-alternative forced choice. A multiple-alternative forced-choice item type follows and is less constrained. This item type is popularized through the traditional multiple-choice item, whereby examinees select a single option out of several alternatives. A multiple-choice item extends easily to a multiple response item by requiring examinees to select a set number of options. This type of multiple response item is still forced-choice because the item stem specifies the number of options to select. Relaxing this last constraint leads to the multiple alternative unforced-choices item type. Conventionally, this is a multiple response item where examinees may select any number of options from a set. We argue that this item type is best suited to assess the construct of cue recognition, the discrimination between information that is relevant or irrelevant to a decision.

Figure 1. An example of alternative and multiple alternative forced- and unforced-choice alternative items. Items are less constrained when the number of alternatives increases and when their choices are unforced.

Decision-making

Rational decision-making demands gathering information as a prerequisite first step. Whether gathering information physically or retrieving it from long term memory, one needs to determine its relevancy. With simple problems, this process is quick and implicit, and it places little burden on the decision maker. More complex problems, however, present decision makers with an abundance of available information. And because of this, efficiently sifting through information and accurately categorizing its relevancy are both vital.

Whether it is implicit and instantaneous or deliberate and time-consuming, the filtering process described above is a form of cue recognition: one recognizes pertinent information and ignores distractors. Therefore, when faced with several pieces of information, decision makers endorse—recognize—the cues relevant to the current decision task but reject those that are irrelevant (e.g., Pleskac, 2007). Ignoring the seemingly unimportant, they consider only information determined as relevant. This is the information that influences decisions, and therefore, they must make well-calibrated choices.

Choosing to attend to incorrect information leads to inappropriate conclusions or actions. Likewise, considering only partial information can lead to decision errors. And although errors can

emerge throughout the entire decision-making process, beginning the process accurately reduces the likelihood of their occurrence in later stages. With two classes of cues, accuracy takes on two forms. In the first class of cues, the valid cues, a correct endorsement is a hit, and failure to endorse a valid cue is a miss. Thus, greater accuracy occurs when decision makers increase their hits and reduce their misses. However, accuracy for valid cues alone is not sufficient; they must consider the other class of cues, the invalid cues. Ignoring an invalid cue results in a correct rejection, whereas endorsing an invalid cue results in a false alarm. The two classes of cues are commonly referred to as signal and noise, and with increased sensitivity to signal, decision makers better discriminate between valid and invalid cues—they properly tease apart signal from noise (see Swets, 2014). Accounting for both types of cues, accuracy increases when maximizing both hits and correct rejections and minimizing both misses and false alarms.

Cognitive psychologists commonly study cue recognition in its most basic form, which allows maximum control over experimental settings. Typically, participants study a list of cues and, after an intervening delay, have their memory tested with a recognition task. The task presents participants with a new list of words, comprising both studied cues (i.e., valid cues) and unstudied cues (i.e., invalid cues) but requires them to select only the studied cues. In other words, participants must endorse only the valid cues and ignore the invalid cues—they perform cue recognition (Pleskac, 2007).

Initially, experimenters scored recognition accuracy by applying a correction method; they subtracted the number of false alarms from the number of hits. Inspecting the endorsement rates of hypothetical participants is the best way to demonstrate the properties of this scoring method. Imagine three participants studied 10 cues and tested over 20 cues, half of which were unstudied. Shown in Figure 2 are the endorsements of hits and false alarms. Participant 1 endorses the most amount of information, correctly identifying all the studied cues but also incorrectly identifying six unstudied cues. The second participant endorses fewer studied and unstudied cues. The last participant endorses the fewest studied cues—less than the other participants—and does not endorse any unstudied cues. The first participant is quite liberal, the second is less so, and the third participant is quite conservative. The dashed line in the

figure represents their corrected score. All three participants earn the same score, despite obvious differences in behavior.

Figure 2. The number of valid and invalid cues recognized by three participants. The dashed line is the corrected score calculated by subtracting invalid cues from valid cues.

Signal-detection theory

To better capture behavioral differences, the field adopted a more intuitive analysis, signal detection theory (for a review, see Swets, 2014). Applying the theory of signal detection to recognition memory requires several basic assumptions. In particular, the theory assumes that cues vary across an underlying memory strength and become endorsed when passing a criterion—a minimum threshold. Because studying valid cues increases their memorability, the distribution of memory strengths for valid cues is greater than for invalid cues, which are unstudied. The general model is shown in Figure 3. With greater sensitivity (d' , d-prime), the distance between valid and invalid cues increases. A neutral placement of the criterion (c) is equally distant from the signal and noise distributions, and bias occurs when the criterion is not perfectly centered. Thus, when measured from the center of the two distributions, positive criterion values indicate conservative cue selection; one needs more evidence—

more memory strength—to endorse cues. Conversely, negative criterion values indicate liberal cue selection, and cue recognition requires relatively little memory strength to surpass the threshold. A signal detection model accounts for both types of cues, valid and invalid, by estimating sensitivity and bias. This avoids a corrected score that conflates liberal with conservative participants.

Figure 3. An illustration of a signal detection theory applied to cue recognition. The measure d' is the distance between the valid (signal) distribution and the invalid (noise) distribution. The measure c is the distance between the center of the two distributions and the response criterion. One recognizes all cues with memory strengths greater than the criterion.

Although psychologists commonly use signal detection models, their experiments typically consist of relatively few participants ($n < 100$). For this reason, researchers maximize the power to detect an effect by collapsing across items, participants, or both; low power prevents item-level or participant-level analyses (Rouder & Lu, 2005; DeCarlo, 2011). By collapsing across these factors, analyses focus on group effects, and participants become nested in experimental conditions. In contrast, psychometricians are interested in item and participant effects; thus, to apply the theory of signal detection, they need more power. Fortunately, moderately sized testing programs easily provide sufficient sample sizes to

accommodate person-level and item-level analyses. Therefore, we developed a signal detection item response model to measure cue recognition by estimating sensitivity and bias parameters for candidates and items. However, the ability of the model to recover true parameters is unknown, but before exploring that issue, we describe the application of signal-detection theory to multiple response items.

Multiple response items

To apply the theory of signal detection to multiple response items, we made the assumption that what underlies cue recognition is the strength of a cue's association to the context (i.e., the probe). And although we make no strict theoretical claims, it stands to reason that, much like in basic recognition experiments, candidates monitor a general familiarity of the cue-to-context association. Thus, when the familiarity of a cue's association surpasses a criterion, a candidate makes an endorsement and indicates that the cue is relevant to the context. For example, if asked to select all the symptoms of a disease, candidates select only those that have symptom-to-disease associations more familiar than some lower bound. Candidates with thresholds set too low select all the presented symptoms, regardless of their validity. To them, all the symptoms have a sufficiently familiar association in the presence of the disease; these candidates recognize cues liberally. In contrast, candidates with thresholds set too high select only strikingly familiar symptoms; these candidates are ultraconservative and recognize too few cues.

Although we use a medical example to illustrate the utility of signal-detection, the framework extends to any application where one must select or identify a subset of information. Consider an aviation example involving air traffic controllers (Bisseret, 1981). One of their objectives—simplified for the sake of illustration—is to monitor incoming and outgoing flights and identify any potential flight hazards. There may be over several dozen planes to monitor contemporaneously, with each plane accompanied by various statistics (e.g., flying altitude, travel speed, etc.). Every unit of information represents a cue and air traffic controllers must identify the cues that could result in a negative event. It is easy to see in this example that the number of cues in a problem set can be quite large.

To specify the signal-detection model, assume the cues are samples from two normal signal and noise distributions with equal variance, the probability of endorsing a cue from the signal distribution is

$$P(y = 1|S) = \Phi((\Psi_S - c)/\tau), \quad (1)$$

such that $y = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if candidate endorses a cue,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$

and Ψ_S representing the mode of the signal distribution, c representing the endorsement criterion, and τ representing a scale parameter (e.g., variance of the signal and noise distributions). Likewise, the probability of endorsing a cue from the noise distribution is

$$P(y = 1|N) = \Phi((\Psi_N - c)/\tau), \quad (2)$$

with Ψ_N representing the mode of the noise distribution and c and τ representing the same criterion and scale parameter. Combining these probabilities, DeCarlo (1998) parameterized a signal detection model in terms of the following generalized linear model:

$$P(y = 1|X) = \Phi\left(\frac{\Psi_N - c}{\tau} + \frac{\Psi_S - \Psi_N}{\tau} X\right), \quad (3)$$

where X takes on the values of 1 for signal cues and 0 for noise cues. Setting Ψ_N to 0 and τ to 1 reduces the model to

$$P(y = 1|X) = \Phi(-c + dX), \quad (4)$$

with d measuring the distance between the noise and signal distribution. As mentioned above, the distance between the two distributions is a measure of a candidate's sensitivity to valid cues; greater distances indicate better cue recognition. However, using the above coding structure for X , the model measures the criterion from the mode of the noise distribution. This complicates interpretation because for the criterion to reflect bias, both signal and noise distributions must be considered. For example, imagine the criterion at a fixed location. As the signal distribution moves further from the noise distribution, the interpretation of the criterion changes. Although the criterion once represented conservative behavior, because of greater separation between the noise and the signal distributions, it now represents liberal behavior. However, setting X to take on the values of .5 for signal cues and -.5 for noise cues results in a model measuring the criterion from the center of the two distributions, accounting for both signal and noise (see Appendix A in DeCarlo, 1998). Now, one interprets the criterion as an indicator of bias, independent of sensitivity.

By extending Equation 4, we have the following signal detection item response model:

$$P(y_{ij} = 1 | c_i, d_i, \alpha_j, \delta_j, \mathbf{X}) = \Phi\left(-c_i + d_i \mathbf{X} - (-\alpha_j + \delta_j \mathbf{X})\right). \quad (5)$$

Let y_{ij} indicate endorsement of a cue for candidate i on item j . Candidate parameters c_i and d_i are the bias and sensitivity parameters for candidate i , with positive values of c_i reflecting conservative responding and larger values of d_i reflecting better discrimination between valid and invalid cues. Item parameters α_j and δ_j are the bias and sensitivity parameters for item j . Like the item difficulty parameter in the Rasch model, δ estimates the difficulty of recognizing cues within an item. In addition, α estimates an item's propensity to solicit conservative or liberal behavior from a participant; a biased item results in candidates' overselecting or underselecting its cues, regardless of cue validity. The vector \mathbf{X} contains the indicator variable for cue status.

An item-level signal detection model can be parameterized and constrained in several ways (see DeCarlo, 2011). In the current research, the following constraints prevented issues with model identifiability and undefined values. First, we modeled items as samples from a population of items, setting μ_α and μ_δ to zero and estimating their variance (i.e., σ_α and σ_δ). Thus, the item parameters are distributed as

$$\alpha_j \sim \text{Normal}(0, \sigma_\alpha), \quad (6)$$

and

$$\delta_j \sim \text{Normal}(0, \sigma_\delta). \quad (7)$$

In a similar manner, candidate parameters are distributed as

$$c_j \sim \text{Normal}(0, \sigma_c), \quad (9)$$

and

$$d_j \sim \text{Normal}(0, \sigma_d). \quad (10)$$

This type of model is commonly referred to as a crossed-random effects model, where both candidates and items are samples from their respective population (Van den Noortgate, De Boeck, & Meulders,

2003). Formulating the model in terms of a generalized linear mixed model allows many popular statistical software packages to estimate its parameters.

To understand the item characteristics of signal detection items, Figure 4 displays the endorsement probability curves of six example items for a candidate varying in sensitivity (ranging from -5 to 5) but with a neutral response bias. The top left panel displays three items with a sensitivity of 0 (i.e., sample mean, and thus average difficulty item) and three different levels of bias: negative, neutral, or positive bias. An item with a negative bias has an increased probability of having its valid cues recognized. However, as displayed in the lower left panel of Figure 4, a negative biased item also has an increased probability of having its invalid cues endorsed. Thus, when faced with a negative biased item, a candidate will over-select cues as being relevant, regardless of whether the cues are relevant or not. The right panel of Figure 4 displays the same items but with an increased sensitivity. Cues for items with higher sensitivity are more difficult to discriminate; relevant cues have a lower probability of being correctly recognized while irrelevant cues have a higher probability of being incorrectly recognized. Similar to other item response models, higher values of candidate sensitivity parameters indicate better cue recognition, and higher values of item sensitivity parameters indicate greater difficulty in cue recognition.

Figure 4. Item characteristic curves for items varying in bias (conservative, neutral, and liberal) and sensitivity (0 and 2). The top panels plot the probability of selecting valid cues, and the bottom panels plot the probability of selecting invalid cues.

Parameter recovery simulation

To understand the viability of using an item-level signal-detection model to score multiple response item data, we carried out a parameter recovery simulation. This straightforward procedure entails generating datasets from known parameters and fitting them with the signal detection model. The degree of discrepancy provides insight as to how capable the model is at recovering true values. Of particular interest in psychometrics, and thus the focus of the paper, is understanding parameter recoverability as a function of sample size, either across candidates, items, or both. Increasing the number of candidates results in greater item precision, and likewise, increasing the number of items per candidate results in greater precision of candidates' latent traits. Items within the signal-detection framework also vary in terms of their nested cue set size. Then, much the same as occurs in testlet models (Wainer &

Kiely, 1987), increasing the number of nested information (i.e., cues for the signal-detection model; items for the testlet model) should result in greater precision of item parameters.

Design

Our objective to recover known parameters across different sample sizes of candidates, items, and item cue set size was accomplished through a fully crossed and balanced three-factorial design with 50 replications across the following factors and levels:

- 1) the number of candidates (N ranged from 100 to 1000 by 100);
- 2) the number of items ($N = 20, 30, \text{ and } 40$); and
- 3) the number of cues within each item ($N = 4, 6, \text{ and } 8$).

For all factors, we held the population distributions constant and generated data from the following parameters:

- 1) item bias parameters were drawn from a

$$\alpha_j \sim \text{Normal}(0, .1);$$

- 2) item sensitivity parameters were drawn from a

$$\delta_j \sim \text{Normal}(0,1);$$

- 3) candidate bias parameters were drawn from a

$$c_j \sim \text{Normal}(0, .3);$$

- 4) candidate sensitivity parameters were drawn from a

$$d_j \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1).$$

Theoretical and practical considerations inspired the population distributions. First, the bias parameters came from a more constrained distribution than the sensitivity parameters. This is because in practice, endorsement bias is much less variable than discrimination between relevant and irrelevant information (see Rotello, Macmillan, Hicks, & Hautus, 2006). Furthermore, we expect greater constraint

on item bias than on candidate bias because of the greater chance of observing offsetting behavior for items than for candidates. It is reasonable to assume that a candidate would exhibit liberal or conservative behavior that is, to some degree, consistent across the test. For each item, however, the number of conservative and liberal candidates will, to some degree, offset each other and thereby cause a regression to the mean effect. Consequently, we model item bias coming from a less variable distribution.

Setting the mean of the sensitivity parameters to zero was done for both computational efficiencies and to prevent undefined values. By setting the means at zero, we were able to efficiently fit the signal-detection model using software package lme4 for R (Bates, Maechler, Bolker, & Walker, 2014). Furthermore, this reduced the likelihood of obtaining inestimable parameters that occurs, for example, when a candidate performs perfectly on all items. That is, as with other item response models, undefined values are common when assessments comprise relatively few observations per candidate and candidates are perfectly accurate or perfectly inaccurate. Although this situation occasionally occurs in psychological research, our goal was to understand sample size requirements under estimable conditions. As such, we used distributions that allowed meeting our objective.

Results

Items.

Turning first to item sensitivity, Figure 5 gives an overview of the general pattern of parameter recovery by plotting the root mean square error (RMSE) across the levels of sample size. As expected, the RMSE becomes smaller as sample size increases. The signal-detection model recovers item sensitivity reasonably well with sample sizes of 400 and greater. However, there are diminishing returns such that samples over 400 yield negligibly smaller RMSE values, a common finding in polytomous IRT models (e.g., the graded response model, Reise & Yu, 1990).

Figure 5. RMSE for the recoverability of item sensitivity (δ) as a function of number of candidates. Red dots indicate outliers.

The number of cues per item also influences RMSE, albeit to a much lesser degree (see Figure 6). In contrast, the number of items per candidate had no influence on RMSE, which we expected because of the independency between items. To analyze the impact of each factor, we subjected the simulation results to an analysis of variance and used this as an approximate method to determine the proportion of variance explained. The number of candidates explained 51% of the variance in the RMSE while the number of cues only explained roughly 10% of the variance. Researches interested in obtaining more precise item sensitivity estimates should place greater priority on sample size than on cue set size.

Figure 6. RMSE for the recoverability of item sensitivity (δ) as a function of number of cues per item.

The general pattern for the item bias parameters across the different levels of sample size is shown in Figure 6. As expected, the range of the RMSE is considerably smaller given the smaller variance in the population distribution. The benefits of greater sample sizes diminish at a similar rate as the sensitivity parameters, producing negligible differences after roughly 400 candidates.

Figure 6. RMSE for the recoverability of item bias (α) as a function of number of candidates. Red dots indicate outliers.

Figure 7 displays the RMSE as a function of the cue set size. The small scale of bias parameters makes it difficult to interpret whether the set size has any meaningful effect. Thus, much like with the sensitivity parameters, we determine the magnitude of impact for each of the factors by computing the explained variance of the factors through an ANOVA. The sample size factor accounted for nearly 66% of the variance in the reduction of RMSE, and the number of cues explained roughly 20% of the variance. The number of items per candidate had no impact on item parameter recovery, as expected.

Figure 7. RMSE for the recoverability of item bias (α) as a function of number of cues per item.

Candidates.

To understand the degree of recoverability of candidate parameters, we conducted similar analyses as the item parameters. That is, we calculated the RMSE for both the candidate sensitivity and bias parameters across the three manipulated factors. We anticipated three general findings. First, the number of candidates in the sample should not have a large impact on the precision of candidate estimates. Although the number of candidates leads to better estimation of item parameters (reduction in the standard error of the estimates) and in turn this should lead to improvements in candidate parameter estimation, this improvement is negligible compared to increasing the number of observations (i.e., items and/or cues within items). Thus, we expect the number of items and cue set size to have a large impact on parameter recoverability. And finally, because the number of observations per candidate is much less than

the number of candidates per item, we anticipate the overall RMSE to be much greater for the candidate parameters than the item parameters.

We tested the first two predictions using an analysis of variance on the RMSE of the candidate sensitivity parameters. Surprisingly, the number of candidates had a statistically significant impact on RMSE, but the effect was quiet small and explained less than 0.01% of the variance. One can view this result as an artifact of too much power. Both the number of items and cue set size had substantially large and equivalent impacts on RMSE (see Figure 8). Each of the factors explained 44% of the variance in RMSE. Lastly, the overall level of RMSE was higher than for item level parameters. The RMSE for the condition that produced the greatest precision for item sensitivity (1,000 candidates and 8 cues per item) was roughly 0.04, but the RMSE for the condition with the greatest precision for candidate sensitivity (40 items and 8 cues per item) was roughly only 0.15. We do not consider this difference concerning and believe that alternative parameterizations the model may reduce the difference in RMSE (e.g., items treated as fixed effects, alternative methods of model estimation).

Figure 8. The RMSE for candidate sensitivity (d) as a function of the number of items and the number of cues per item.

The same predictions applied to candidate bias parameters, despite the differences in the population scale (i.e., population variance). An analysis of variance yielded the same statistically significant effect of the number of candidates, despite its negligible impact; it explained less than 0.001% of the variance. Again, we view this as an artifact of too much power. Figure 9 shows the RMSE as a function of the number of items and cue set size, both of which produced reliable impacts on parameter recovery, and both factors explained the same amount of variance (46%). As with the sensitivity parameters, we expected higher levels of RMSE for candidates than for items. The mean for the condition with the most precise item bias parameter (1,000 candidates and 8 cues per item) was roughly 0.02 and

the candidate bias parameter in the most precise condition (40 items and 8 cues per item) was roughly 0.07.

Figure 9. The RMSE for candidate bias (c) as a function of the number of items and the number of cues per item.

Conclusions

The simulation results are promising for the application of an item-level signal-detection model. Under the simulate conditions, reasonable item parameter recovery is achievable with 400 candidates and reasonable candidate parameter recovery is achievable with 40 items. However, the population distributions used for data generation were ideal for the objectives of the study. In practice, the true population distribution may not be normal and therefore not as ideal as they were in this study. For

example, the population of candidate sensitivity may not be normally distributed because it is likely that some lower degree of discriminability between relevant and irrelevant information exists. Figure 8 shows two hypothetical population distributions, a normal distribution and a skewed distribution. If the true population distribution is skewed, then fitting a normal model produces asymmetrical shrinkage to the population mean. A solution is to model the candidate parameters as fixed effects (using GLMM terms), that is, without a population distribution. Although this contrasts typical IRT parameterization, where the candidates are sampled from the population, it makes for more interpretable candidate parameters, and, not withstanding differences in stimuli, is more comparable to psychological experiments.

Psychological researchers have been applying signal-detection models to cognitive based data for nearly 60 years (cf. Swets, 2014). However, most experiments are small sample studies and therefore researchers must collapse across either items, participants, or both. The lack of power prevented more item-level analyses. Because an experimentalist's subject pool is a scarce resource, researchers in these fields have had trouble recruiting large samples for experimentation and therefore analyses occur through simpler statistical models. But with the growing trend of recruiting experimental subjects via internet methods (e.g., Amazon's MTurk; Buhrmester, Kwang & Gosling, 2011), sample size limitations may be a thing of the past. This would allow psychological researchers to adopt a wider range of item-level analyses.

One potential model is an item-level signal-detection model. DeCarlo (2010; 2011) describes various extensions of signal-detection, including random coefficient models like the one used in the current study. However, there is little research on the precision and sample size requirements of these models. The current study determined that adequate performance is achievable with sample sizes of 400 candidates and at least 40 items. Furthermore, researches can achieve greater precision by increases the cue set per each item. The result of this study seem promising and future simulations exploring alternative signal-detection parameterizations would benefit the field.

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